

Factors Affecting Consumer Buying Behavior towards Local Brands in Zambia: A Consideration of the Product Preference

Burton Mweemba¹, Dr. Geoffrey Mweshi², Professor Edwin Bbenkele³

^{1,2,3}ZCAS University

P.O. Box 35243, Lusaka, Zambia

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 07 April 2022</p> <p>Corresponding Author: Burton Mweemba</p> <p>KEYWORDS: Consumer buying behavior, Fast Moving Consumer Goods, Imported, Quality, Availability, Price</p>	<p>Recent economic growth trends in Africa have heightened industry awareness of the market potential of many African countries including Zambia. As a result, academics are becoming increasingly interested in learning about African customers' attitudes, tastes, and behavior. The majority of the investigations on the factors affecting consumer behavior have been done predominantly from the Western marketing viewpoints, and the results have been informative in the sense that they confirmed and extended existing marketing models. In view of this, this paper brings out the Zambian perspective of consumer buying behavior. There has been an increase in the sale of imported FMCGs in Zambia, hence this motivated the investigation on the factors that motivate consumers when buying the products. The results indicate that quality, price, and availability influence consumer buying behavior in Zambia. The results further suggest that consumers in Zambia prefer imported FMCGs. The recommendation, therefore, is that manufacturers should take into consideration the factors affecting consumer behavior when producing FMCGs. The gap in understanding consumer buying behavior in less developed countries like Zambia has existed since 1986 when Bbenkele (1986) found that product shortages had an impact on brand loyalty in Zambia.</p>

I. INTRODUCTION

Consumers make purchase decisions on a daily basis. Qazzafi (2020) postulated that some of the consumers could even be unaware of the factors that affect their decision on a specific product, service, or brand. According to Tanksale, Neelam, and Venkarachalam (2014), purchase consumer decision-making is a combination of mental orientation and product choice. According to Domie (2013), consumer decision making relates to how people, groups, and organizations select, purchase, utilize, and discard items, ideas, and services to suit their needs and desires, and Kumar & Joseph (2014) added that consumer decision making is the pre-purchase activity that precedes the intention to buy or consume. It is therefore important for businesses to understand the factors that affect consumer behavior.

II. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

i. To establish the factors affecting consumer behavior towards FMCGs in Zambia

ii. To establish the product preference between local and imported brands in Zambia

III. METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a positivist philosophical paradigm. The positivist research philosophy asserts that the social world can be comprehended objectively. The scientist is an objective analyst in this research philosophy, and on the basis of it, he dissociates himself from personal values and works independently (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2016). This study was quantitative in nature and collected the data using a questionnaire. For this study, the researcher used a survey other than a case study. According to Check and Schutt (2012), survey research is the collection of information from a sample of individuals gotten from a large population. Surveys as a research strategy allow researchers to collect data using quantitative research strategies. In this study, the target population was the buyers of Fast-Moving Consumer Goods in the Lusaka district.

Sampling is the process of choosing a representative group of people or items from the population of interest in order to

generalize the findings (Etikan & Bala, 2017). For this study, the researcher used probability (systematic) when collecting quantitative data from consumers of FMCGs. For this study, the sample size was 295 respondents.

IV. LITERATURE REVIEW

Consumers typically make purchasing decisions on a daily basis, and Qazzafi (2020) suggests that many of them are unaware of the factors that influence their decision-making on a particular product, service, or brand. Consumer decision-making is said to be a combination of mental orientation and product choice (Tanksale, Neelam, and Venkarachalam, 2014). In his study, Domie (2013) stated that consumer decision-making relates to how individuals, groups, and organizations select, purchase, utilize, and discard products, ideas, and services to suit their needs and desires. According to Kumar & Joseph (2014), consumer decision-making is the activity that occurs before a purchase or consumption decision is made. When it comes to the emotional and psychological requirements that matter to a particular customer, Nyarko, Asiamah, Agbemava, and Tsetse (2015) discovered that consumer decision-making functions as need arousal.

Kotler & Keller (2016) postulated that there are a lot of factors that affect consumer buying behavior and these include; culture, social, personal, and psychological factors.

Figure 2.1 Factors influencing consumer buying behavior

Source: Kotler & Armstrong (2012)

1) Common factors that influence consumer purchase behavior as identified by other researchers

According to Domie (2013), when it comes to consumer buying behavior, the country of origin of a product is more essential. Nguyen & Gizaw (2014) Found that consumer desire to buy is influenced by price and quality. A study by Dudovskiy (2015) discovered a link between previous experience and customer purchase behaviors. Debasis (2015) established that high and low involvement goods are associated to gender, family structure, and family decision-making. Yoon & Carpenter (2013) looked at the impact of aging on consumer decision-making. Personal consuming preferences and practices, for example, are key cultural intermediates in purchasing decisions (Richard & Masud, 2016). Narsey & Russell (2011) found that consumer

consumption is influenced by varying levels of self-reflexive consciousness.

Amankwah (2017) in his study found that brand name, price, confidence, promotion, loyalty, and brand satisfaction all influence customer purchasing behavior. In a related study, Adofo (2014) found the packaging of a beauty product to increase consumer usage. Darko (2012) claims that the proper selection of sales promotional tools has a significant impact on purchase behavior. Nyarko, Asiamah, Agbemava, & Tsetse (2015) found that celebrity endorsement is very enticing and influential in influencing consumer purchasing behavior. Most importantly, celebrity endorsement influences consumer purchasing decisions. Bajde & Ottlewski (2016) posit that social-economic aspects influence the consumer decision-making process while purchasing FMCGs.

According to Heetkamp & Tusveld (2011), some customers buy products based on the country of origin (COO), and Sheith (2011) claims that certain buyers associate quality with certain countries' brands over others. One of the aspects influencing a customer's purchase decision is their understanding of the benefits of buying particular brands. Kibret (2016) suggests that some consumers pay more attention to the quality of a brand than they do to the price as a sign of status.

a) Personal factor

Personal factors that influence customer purchasing behavior include; age and life cycle phases, occupation, attitude, lifestyle, and values (Kotler, Keller, Brady, Goodman, & Hansen, 2019). This is a result of a combination of direct and indirect personal influences. Others have a direct influence on customer purchasing behavior, while others have an indirect influence. Therefore, Kotler & Keller (2016) posit that businesses should be aware of personal influences because they impact customers' day-to-day purchasing decisions.

b) Psychological factor

Another key factor that has an influence on customer purchasing behavior is the psychological factor. According to Ali & Ramya (2016), psychological factors are considered to be internal. Kotler & Keller (2016) postulate that the environment has a significant effect in influencing a consumer's purchasing behavior. The purchases of other buyers of goods or services have a big impact on people. For instance, the "other customer" could be a friend, family member, or coworker (Rani, 2014). According to Kotler and Keller (2016), psychological factors include motivation, perception, learning, and memory.

c) Social factor

The social factor is one of the most important determinants of consumer buying behavior. According to Kotler & Keller (2016), "social factor" refers to a person's neighborhood, social network, online networks, friends, and family. Rani (2016) suggests that the social factor mostly includes the use

of word-of-mouth to influence customer purchase decisions. Word-of-mouth is the most powerful influencer of customer buying decisions. Other people, such as salespeople from a firm, may have a bigger influence on a person's relatives or friends. A person's faith in his or her relatives or friends is greater than his or her faith in strangers. It becomes important for business players to appreciate the importance of the social factors in influencing consumer buying behavior.

d) Economic factor

A consumer's financial status influences his or her purchasing decision and preference for a certain brand or product (Ali & Ramya, 2016). Companies should be able to conduct research on customer spending and saving behavior. Normally, consumers will purchase items that they can afford. Personal income, family income, income goals, investments, consumer credit, and other economic variables should all be considered.

2) Factors influencing consumer behavior when buying local products in Indonesia

According to Dwi and Nyoman (2020), the Indonesian government created the buy local campaign or program to encourage people to purchase more local agricultural products. Indonesian consumers favor locally produced goods over imported goods (Dwiastari, Susrusa, & Artini, 2019; Sumarwan & Palupi, 2017; Monalisa, 2015). According to Dwi & Nyoman's (2020) study, price is the most important factor influencing local customers. Taste, color, size, income level, and product availability were all major characteristics that led Indonesian consumers to buy local agricultural products.

Local agricultural goods are also consumed by the tourism accommodation sector, such as hotels and restaurants. Some of the elements that drive demand for local fruit in starred hotels include quality, pricing, hotel policy, continuity, and government policies, with quality being the most important one (Sumawidari, Darmawan, & Astiti, 2013). According to Wirawan, Julyasih, Adiartayasa, Wijaya, & Anom (2014), numerous factors influence customer buying behavior in Indonesia, with packaging, transportation, and quality being the most important. This study, however, was conducted on the agriculture sector in Indonesia, a country with a different environment than Zambia, and it is focused on the general FMCG industry.

According to Dwi & Nyoman (2020), there are few studies on the factors that influence consumer behavior in developing nations when it comes to buying locally made goods. Nonetheless, the results of studies on the factors that impact the purchasing of local products in developing nations are comparable to those found in developed countries (Arsil, Li, & Bruwer, 2016).

For a long time, studies on the importance of buying local products have been prominent in industrialized countries.

Most of the time, this is motivated by concern for the well-being of local producers who face negative impact of the business environment towards their businesses. As a result, consumer preferences for local agricultural goods in developed countries such as the United States and the United Kingdom have been thoroughly established. According to Dwi & Nyoman (2020), there are still few studies on the factors that influence the purchasing and consumption of locally produced products in developing nations.

3) Factors influencing consumer behavior when buying local products in India

According to a study conducted in India by Vijayalakshmi, Gurumoorthy, Lingavel, Arulmozhi, & Kannan (2020), the FMCG sector has become competitive as customers' preferences for local cuisine have shifted. The goal of the study was to investigate the factors that influence customer behavior when it comes to buying local foods. Consumers in India were influenced by quality, price, flavor, and availability while purchasing FMCGs. This study agreed with Kumar & Joseph (2014) in terms of quality being the most important contributing factor, however it differed in terms of other influencing factors. Their study found that consumers were influenced to buy local FMCG's by quality (68%), attitude (67%), brand loyalty (58%), and packaging (23%). The studies varied as a result of one having been done in a rural environment (Vijayalakshmi, Gurumoorthy, Lingavel, Arulmozhi, & Kannan, 2020) and the other in the urban setting (Kumar & Joseph, 2014).

In another study conducted in India, Sarker & Rahman (2017) found that a number of factors influenced consumers' purchasing behavior when it came to personal care items. Consumers, including those from the middle- and lower-income levels, believe that television commercials, followed by quality and brand loyalty, are the most important factors that influence consumer buying behavior towards care products in India. Islam, Perveen, Islam, & Ahamed (2015) posit that customers consider brand image, cost and obligations, distinctiveness, reputation, and customer relationship while purchasing an FMCG. According to another study by Khare & Ali (2018), many FMCG consumers in India prefer local to foreign products because of product quality, price, and brand name. This study agrees with Kumar & Joseph's (2014) study, which indicated that price, quality, and brand name had a significant impact on FMCG customers in India.

4) Factors influencing consumer behavior when buying local products in Malaysia

Malaysia's annual gross domestic product (GDP) has been gradually increasing over the years, and it was found that the food and beverage (F&B) industry contributes to the growth of Malaysia's GDP. Malaysia's food and beverage retail business was predicted to continue growing. Rose,

Zariyawati, Norazlina, Annuar, & Manisah (2016) conducted a study in Malaysia to see if Malaysian consumers embrace locally manufactured FMCGs marketed by small and medium enterprises (SME). According to the study's findings on the factors that influence consumer buying behavior, quality came in first with 51%, followed by price with 40%, branding with 5%, packaging with 3%, and others with 1%. Customers prioritized quality and branding while purchasing local FMCGs in a city with a population of over 30 million. According to Wu & Jang (2013), when a customer wants to buy a product, they prefer to buy something that is durable, even if it is more expensive because they believe such things provide better value for money.

According to a study conducted by Dobbelstein, Mason, & Kamwendo (2020) in Germany and South Africa to better understand consumer attitudes and factors influencing FMCG preferences, respondents from both countries preferred local brands, believing that they were of higher quality and better linked to local community development. South Africans are more aware of this, are more dedicated to local FMCGs, and are willing to pay more than Germans. The study found that respondents' considered quality, value for money, and trust in local brands as important factors influencing consumer buying behavior. Another study by Cranfield, Henson, & Blandon (2012) found that product branding, quality, convenience, price, and the presence or absence of safety issues can all influence whether or not local FMCGs are purchased by local consumers.

According to Dobbelstein, Mason, and Kamwendo (2020), there is minimal difference between the two countries in terms of judgments of relative quality, value for money, and confidence in local firms, and both sets of respondents had more positive perceptions of local brands. Despite the fact that neither the South African nor the German respondents favor higher-priced products or believe that higher prices imply higher quality, they both agree that paying more for high-quality goods is desirable, and that a brand name may signal quality. South Africans, unlike Germans, believe that price is a greater measure of quality.

It's also likely that consumers in industrialized countries are more sophisticated when it comes to judging the quality of branded items, whereas consumers in developing countries are less sophisticated and still consider price as a quality indication (Marian, Chrysochou, Krystallis, & Thogersen, 2014). Both South African and German respondents thought the brand attributes of integrity, repute, benevolence, and attitude were important, which supported the findings of Charton-Vachet and Lombart (2018).

5) Factors influencing consumer buying behavior in Africa

In recent years, investor interest in the retail and consumer industries in Sub-Saharan Africa has expanded (PwC Africa,

2016). Previously, the region's concentration was on extractive sectors such as oil and mining, but a growing consumer class seeking everything from mobile phones to fast food has caused many retailers and consumer goods businesses to take a fresh look at the region. According to KPMG (2016), the FMCG business in Africa has developed, with households spending an average of 44% of their monthly income on FMCGs, indicating that the industry has the potential to assist grow local economies if correctly managed. The report suggests that consumers in Sub-Saharan Africa are also becoming more ambitious and brand-conscious. Consumers are now paying greater attention to brands, packaging, and product features, rather than price, which was once the most important factor in influencing consumer buying behavior.

6) Factors influencing consumer buying behavior in Kenya

Angasa & Kinoti (2013) investigated the factors that influence consumer purchasing decisions in Kenya. The detergents as a type of FMCG were the focus of the investigation. The study found that quality and price had a major impact on customers' buying decisions. Another study in Kenya indicated that product type and price had a substantial impact on respondents' purchase decisions, as evidenced by mean scores of 4.50 and 3.92, respectively (Mutheu, 2014). In contrast, the majority of respondents indicated that factors such as country of origin, family influence, product packaging, advertisement, and promotions had only a minor impact on their purchasing decisions, as reflected by mean scores of 3.42, 3.38, 3.33, and 3.00, respectively.

7) Factors influencing consumer buying behavior in Ghana

In Ghana, a study was done to establish the factors that influence customer buying behavior for local FMCGs. Amankwah (2016) found that consumer buying behavior was influenced by country of origin, brand name, quality, and price. This study agreed with Kumar & Joseph (2014) who found that Indian customers were heavily impacted by country of origin, product quality, product price, and brand name when buying FMCGs.

Another study was conducted to determine why consumers preferred imported FMCGs over indigenous ones. According to Domie (2013), some Ghanaian customers purchased more foreign or imported products due to the following factors: non-availability of a local product (1%), poor packaging (17%), poor quality (59%), health concerns (14%), and comparatively high costs (19%). The issue of poor quality is at the top of the list. According to Elliot and Cameron (1994), items must be of acceptable quality for consumers to be ethnocentric, while Kotler & Keller (2006) stated that product price is a significant component in influencing consumers to buy local FMCGs.

“Factors Affecting Consumer Buying Behavior towards Local Brands in Zambia: A Consideration of the Product Preference”

Other consumers value quality over product affordability (Sethna & Blythe, 2016). Another study, on the other hand, have revealed that both price and quality have a substantial influence on customer buying behavior when it comes to purchasing FMCGs (Albari & Safitri, 2018; Owusu, 2013).

8) Factors influencing consumer buying behavior in Zimbabwe

Karedza & Sikwila (2017) investigated the factors that influence consumer buying behavior in Zimbabwe, particularly when the country encountered major economic hardships. The study found that price had a greater impact on customer purchasing behavior in Zimbabwe than any other component. The survey also discovered that quality and accessibility had an impact on FMCG customers' purchasing behavior. Due to Zimbabwe's struggling economy, price may have affected consumers more than any other aspect. Another aspect that was discovered to have a major impact on consumer behavior was product packaging. Makanyeza (2016) conducted a similar study and found that product accessibility, price, health concerns, country of origin, product labeling, packaging, and branding were major factors that influenced food consumer purchase behavior in Zimbabwe. This study was supported by Karedza & Sikwila's (2017) findings that accessibility, price, quality, and packaging are all factors that influence consumer purchasing decisions.

9) Factors affecting consumer buying behavior in Zambia

In his study on consumer behavior in less developed countries, Bbenkele (1986) found that product shortages affected brand loyalty in Zambia. He found that income and product availability greatly affected consumer loyalty. However, the gap still remains as there has been no further study done on consumer behavior in Zambia as the country has undergone numerous economic and demographic changes.

V. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This section of the paper explains the theoretical constructs that underpin the research. A theory is a systematic collection of information given progressively and logically to explain a phenomenon and assist society in rationally interpreting events. The theories in a study anchor or give a firm foundation for an academic scholarship. Adom, Kamil, & Agyem (2018) posit that a theoretical framework also defines the philosophy of the study, by attempting to contextualize and apply the available conceptual structure as a guide.

According to Ravitch & Carl (2016), the theoretical framework is a crucial component of proper research since it provides proof of the existing structure that is relevant to the researchers' domain. According to Smith (2004), it is difficult for the researcher to effectively relate the study to the available literature without a theoretical framework because this structure gives the needed guide to the current investigation (Miller, 2007).

1. Engel, Kollat, and Blackwell (1968) buyer decision process model

The "buyer decision-making process," is the procedure that customers follow before making a purchase (Kotler, 2012). Marketers have been paying close attention to consumer purchasing habits. According to Blackwell, Miniard, and Engel (2006), the buyer decision process, is one of the numerous models designed to examine consumer behavior. According to Vindigni, Janssen, and Jager (2002), there has been a rise in consumer behavior research particularly in the food sector. Engel, Kollat, and Blackwell (1968) were the first to suggest the concept of the consumer buying decision process. The model has gone through various changes that, if effectively implemented, will assist marketers in developing effective marketing strategies, communications mix, and product branding strategies (Blackwell, Miniard & Engel, 2006).

Figure 1. EKB Model

Source: Engel, Kollat, & Blackwell (1968) buyer decision process

“Factors Affecting Consumer Buying Behavior towards Local Brands in Zambia: A Consideration of the Product Preference”

The EKB model is divided into three sections: information input and processing, decision variables (internal and external), and decision process, the latter of which is the subject of this study, and the others are influencing elements in the decision process. External stimuli deliver information to the consumer's mind, where it is processed (Nageswari, 2019). An intention and a purchase are the outcomes of interactions between new knowledge, attitudes, personality, beliefs, previous experience, and the influence of contextual

circumstances. Engel, Kollat, & Blackwell (1973) presented the customer as a decision-making unit in the process of locating, evaluating, and purchasing a product. Information input, information processing, decision making, variables influencing decision making, and external impacts were the primary variables in the model. The EKB model has a limitation in that it presupposes that buyers are always rational when making purchases.

Buyer decision process

Figure 2. Buyer decision process
Source: Kotler (2012)

Need recognition is the first step in the decision-making process for the customer. It is sometimes called problem recognition. Customers' requirements or needs should be recognized, and the company should try to satisfy them (Shma, 2012). Consumers' search for information is the second step in the purchasing process. Customers recall their past ideas about a product when they go to buy products or services; if the previous experience was positive or pleasant, and the customer was satisfied, the consumer purchases the product, and the search for knowledge is completed. Chen (2012) claims that buyers begin looking for information when they have a need for a product. However, this is the stage marketers should ensure that they appreciate the factors that influence consumer buying behavior. At this phase, data is gathered from a variety of consumer-accessible sources. Kotler (2017) postulate that consumers gather information from a variety of sources, including family, friends, neighbors, advertisements, sales promotions, mass media, and social media.

Evaluation of alternatives is the third level of the consumer's purchase decision-making process. It follows the knowledge search, which is the second stage of the purchase decision-making process. When a buyer learns about a product or a brand, he or she reviews it before deciding whether or not to buy it. According to Chen (2012), based on the customer's experience with the product, they may explore other alternatives or repurchase the product.

In his study in China, Chen (2012) stated that consumers only supported the consumption of organic foods when they were informed of the health benefits. Only by using efficient

promotional strategies while appreciating the factors influencing consumer behavior will the Zambian manufacturing sector be able to gain support from local customers. Consumers' purchase decision is the fourth stage of the purchasing decision-making process. After acquiring information from a number of sources, assessing it, and determining when and how to buy, the buyer decides to buy the product. According to Kotler (2012), consumers make purchasing decisions after carefully evaluating many brand alternatives. When making a purchasing decision, consumers often consider factors such as the store's location, image, product pricing, and customer service (Shinde & Markle, 2012).

The final stage is called the post-purchase decision. Companies sometimes believe that their relationship with customers ends once a purchase decision has been made. Kotler (2012) posit that companies should be aware of their clients' attitude toward their products that come as a result of being satisfied or dissatisfied with the goods or service. A satisfied client is more likely to purchase more of the same brand in the future, and a happy customer may thus convince others to buy the brand through word of mouth (WOM). According to Kotler & Armstrong (2011), customer satisfaction has a favorable impact on product sales, which further positively impacts the profits. The decision-making model has flaws in that it assumes that consumers make decisions in a rational way and evaluate products logically. The model also fails to consider impulse buying by consumers.

2. *Modification of the consumer decision-making process*

Customers go through a common mental process when deciding to buy a product or service, as developed by Engel, Kollat, & Blackwell in 1968 (Darley, Blackson, & Luethge, 2010). Hoffman and Bateson (2016) took a fresh look at the consumer decision-making process. This paradigm

Figure 3. Modified decision-making process
Source: Hoffman & Bateson (2016)

Although Hoffman & Bateson (2017) used other terms for some of the original stages of this process (for example, choice instead of the purchase decision and problem awareness instead of need recognition), the meaning of what happens in these steps remains the same. As a result, the model has transformed into one that is internet-based, complex, and fast. The rise of social media has altered the old model of consumer decision-making significantly (Bassiouni & Hackley, 2014). By including stimuli and the model being influenced by social media, Hoffman & Bateson's (2014) model adds a new layer to understanding consumer behavior. In today's world, social media cannot be overlooked as a potential media platform for influencing customer behavior towards local products.

VI. ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

Factors influencing consumer behavior towards FMCGs in Zambia

Table 1. Factors influencing consumer behavior in Zambia

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Packaging	32	11.0	13.9	13.9
Quality	146	50.0	63.2	77.1
Price	11	3.8	4.8	81.8
Valid Accessibility	35	12.0	15.2	97.0
Others Specify	6	2.1	2.6	99.6
12	1	.3	.4	100.0
Total	231	79.1	100.0	
Missing System	61	20.9		
Total	292	100.0		

Table 1 above shows the descriptive statistics on the reasons why consumers prefer foreign FMCGs compared to local brands. 50% of respondents cited quality as the primary reason for purchasing imported FMCGs, 12.0%, cited accessibility as the main factor affecting the choice of FMCGs. 11% of respondents cited packaging, 3.8% cited price and other reasons were cited by only 6 respondents

substituted need recognition with problem awareness, and it was no longer the first stage in the consumer decision-making process. Before identifying a need or problem, consumers are motivated by stimuli such as advertising or social cues. In other words, a specific stimulus or group of stimuli initiates the detection of a problem, resulting in a six-step process rather than the initial five.

(2.1%). The findings of this study are almost similar to those of other studies conducted in India, Malaysia, Indonesia, and Ghana. Quality was the most important factor influencing consumer purchasing behavior in India, Malaysia, and Ghana, with 68%, 51%, and 59% respectively (Dwi & Nyoman, 2020; Sarker & Rahman, 2017; Domie, 2013). Packaging came in second with 23% in China, followed by attitude with 8%. 40% of respondents cited price as a factor affecting consumer behavior in Malaysia, followed by branding (5%), packaging (3%), and other factors (1%). According to a comparative study in Ghana and South Africa, quality, price, and design were important factors influencing consumers' purchase preferences with mean scores of 4, 4.46, and 4.2, respectively (Darku & Akpan, 2020).

Table 2. Customers product preference

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Local	61	20.9	20.9	20.9
Valid Foreign	231	79.1	79.1	100.0
Total	292	100.0	100.0	

The descriptive statistics in Table 2 show which FMCGs customers purchase the most. Local brands are preferred by 20.9%, whereas foreign or imported FMCGs are preferred by 77.1% of respondents. Table 1 shows that consumers purchase imported FMCGs for three reasons: quality (50%), accessibility (12%), and packaging (11%). The results in table 2 suggest that consumers support the imported brands due to good quality, product availability, and packaging. According to the study by Van den Berg (2017) in South Africa, 24% of the respondents strongly disagreed with a statement that buying foreign brands is un- South African, 38% disagreed and 24% neither disagreed nor agreed. Both

studies seem to have their respondents supporting imported brands as compared to local products.

VII. DISCUSSION

Understanding factors that affect consumer buying behavior has become of great importance if businesses are to satisfy the needs of customers. Customers are influenced by a product's perceived value while buying. There are many factors that affect customers while purchasing products and these include; product quality, packaging, and accessibility as indicated in table 1.

According to Dwi & Nyoman (2020), there are few studies done on the factors that influence consumer behavior in developing countries when it comes to purchasing locally produced FMCGs. Despite this, the findings of these studies on the factors that impact the purchase of local FMCGs in developing countries are comparable to those found in developed countries (Arsil, Li, & Bruwer, 2016). The findings in table 2 show that many consumers prefer buying foreign brands as compared to local brands. It can be deduced that consumers' preference for imported FMCGs brands could be as a result of poor-quality products available, unavailability of preferred brands, and poor packaging.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The consumers in developing countries such as Zambia have also become complex with regard to their purchase behavior. Businesses dealing in FMCGs would do themselves a disservice if little or no effort is put into understanding the factors that affect consumers' behavior towards the purchase of local FMCGs. The findings indicate that consumers of FMCGs in Zambia would only buy products of acceptable quality and should be available when needed. This being the case, the industry players should improve on the production of quality products and enhance the supply chain.

REFERENCES

1. Albari, N., & Safitri, I. (2018). The influence of price on consumers purchasing decisions. *Review of Integrative Business and Economics Research*, 7(2), 328-337.
2. Adofo, A. O. (2014). The effect of beauty product packaging on consumer buying decision: A case of selected shops in the New Juabeng Municipality, Ghana. *The Business & Management Review*, 5(3), 14.
3. Ali, M. A., & Ramya, N. (2016). Factors affecting consumer buying behavior. *International Journal of Applied Research*, 2(10), 76-80.
4. Amankwah, M. O. (2017). *Determinants of Purchase Decisions of Consumers of the Products of Nestle Ghana*. Accra.
5. Angasa, A., & Kinoti, W. (2013). Factors Affecting Consumer Perception Of Kenyan Manufactured Fast Moving Consumer Goods In The East African Community. A Case of Laundry Detergents Products. *DBA Africa Management Review*, 3(2), 108-123.
6. Arsil, P., Li, E., & Bruwer, J. (2016). Perspectives on consumer perceptions of local foods: a view from Indonesia. *Journal of International Food & Agribusiness Marketing*, 26(2), 107-124.
7. Bajde, D., & Ottlewski, L. (2016). Cultural challenges of social-economic innovation: The Case of Housing for help. *Consumer Culture Theory*, 18, 93-107.
8. Bassiouni, D., & Hackley, C. (2014). Eration Z children's adaptation to digital consumer culture: A critical literature review. *Journal of Consumer Behavior*, 13(2), 113-133.
9. Bbenkele, E. (1986). *Understanding consumer behavior in less developed countries: An empirical investigation of the Brand loyalty in Zambia*. The University of Stirling OF STIRLING.
10. Blackwell, R. (2001). *Consumer behaviour* (10 ed.). Thompson South Western: Mason. Retrieved from <http://www.scielo.org.za/pdf/acom/v17n1/22.pdf>
11. Charton-Vachet, F., & Lombart, C. (2018). Impact of the link between individuals and their region on the customer-regional brand relationship. *Journal of Retailing & Consumer Services*, 43, 170-187.
12. Check, J., & Schutt, R. K. (2012). *Research methods in Education*. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications.
13. Cranfield, J., Henson, S., & Blandon, J. (2012). The effect of attitudinal and sociodemographic factors on the likelihood of buying locally produced food. *Agribusiness*, 28(2), 205-221.
14. Darko, E. (2012). *The Influence of Sales Promotion on Consumer Buying Behaviour in the Telecom Industry: The Case of Vodafone Ghana*. Accra.
15. Darku, E., & Akpan, W. (2020). Selling culture: A buy local campaigns in the Ghanaian and South African textile and clothing industries. *Journal of Enterprising Communities*, 14(4), 643-662.
16. Darley, W., Blackson, C., & Luethge, D. J. (2010). Towards an integrated framework for online consumer behavior and decision making: A review. *Psychology and Marketing*, 27(2), 94-116.
17. Debasis, B. (2015). Impact of different facets of product involvement and consideration set on teens family purchase decision making: A multivariate analysis. *African Journal of Marketing Management*, 7(3), 32-41.

“Factors Affecting Consumer Buying Behavior towards Local Brands in Zambia: A Consideration of the Product Preference”

18. Dobbstein, T., Mason, R. B., & Kamwendo, A. (2020). Consumer perceptions of critical success factors for small local consumer brands. *Studia Universitatis Babes-Bolyai Oeconomica*, 65(2), 66-76.
19. Domie, S. P. (2013). *Assessing the factors that influences consumer switch from local to imported products: A case study of Kasapreko Company Limited-Ghana*. Accra.
20. Dudovskiy, J. (2015). Review Consumer Behavior and Factors Affecting on Purchasing Decisions. *Singaporean Journal of Business Economics*, 10(1), 15.
21. Dwi, M., & Nyoman, Y. N. (2020). *Factors affecting the purchase of local agricultural commodities*. Bali: University of Udayana.
22. Elliott, G., & Cameron, R. C. (1994). Consumer perception of product quality and country-of origin effect. *Journal of International Marketing*, 2(2), 49-62.
23. Engel, J., Kollat, D. T., & Blackwell, R. D. (1968). *Consumer behavior*. New York: Rinehart & Winston.
24. Etikan, I., & Bala, K. (2017). Sampling and sampling methods. *Biometrics and Biostatistics International Journal*, 5(6), 215-222.
25. Heetkamp, A., & Tusveld, L. R. (2011). Origin Management: Rules of origin in free trade agreement. *Irish Journal of Management*, 10, 41-72.
26. Hoffman, K., & Bateson, J. E. (2016). *Services marketing: concepts, strategies and cases* (5 ed.). Boston: Cengage Learning.
27. Islam, M., Perveen, R., Islam, S. M., & Ahamed, B. (2015). Factors affecting consumers purchasing decision of toiletries products: an empirical study on square toiletries in khulna city. *Elixir International Journal*, 72-80.
28. Karedza, G., & Sikwila, M. (2017). The Impact of Packaging Designs on Consumer Buying behaviour of FMCG during the hyperinflationary and after the dollarisation era in Zimbabwe. *Asian Journal of Social Sciences and Management Studies*, 4(1), 20-30.
29. Khare, P., & Ali, S. (2018). Factor influencing Customer preference for FMCG in Reference to KAVAL Towns. *International Journal of Latest Engineering and Management Research*, 3(3), 37-41.
30. KPMG Report. (2016). *The FMCG products with huge growth potential in Africa*. London: Haymarket Network Ltd.
31. Kotler, P. (2017). *Principles of Marketing* (Seventh European Edition ed.). Harlow: Pearson Education.
32. Kotler, P., & Armstrong, G. (2011). *Principles of Marketing* (14 ed.). Prentice Hall: Pearson Education Limited.
33. Kotler, P., & Keller, L. K. (2016). *Marketing management* (15 ed.). Pearson Education.
34. Kotler, P., Keller, L. K., Brady, M., Goodman, M., & Hansen, T. (2019). *Marketing management* (Fourth European Edition ed.). Pearson Education.
35. Kibret, A. (2016). Consumer ethnocentrism tendency in Africa: A Literature Review. *Global Journal of Commerce and Management Perspective*, 5(1), 97-106.
36. Kumar, N., & Joseph, J. (2014). A study on consumer behavior towards FMCG products among the rural-suburban Hhs of Ernakulam. *Journal of Global Economics*, 2-10.
37. Makanyeza, C. (2016). Factors influencing consumers' choice of imported poultry meat products in a developing market: Lessons from Zimbabwe. *Agricultural Economics Research, Policy and Practice in Southern Africa*, 55(3), 191-215.
38. Marian, L., Chrysochou, P., Krystallis, A., & Thøgersen, J. (2014). The role of price as a product attribute in the organic food context: An exploration based on actual purchase data. *Food Quality and Preference*, 37, 52-60.
39. Monalisa, T. (2015). Factors affecting consumer buying behavior towards local products. *Journal of Food Products Marketing*, 196-215.
40. Mutheu, J. (2014). *The influence of country of origin of Fast Moving Consumer Goods FMCG's on consumer purchase decisions in Kenya*. Nairobi: University of Nairobi.
41. Nageswari, R. (2019). The evolution of consumer behavior in digital the age. *UGC Journal*, 7(1), 245-251.
42. Narsey, V., & Russell, C. A. (2011). Realistically fake: Self-reflexive consciousness, ironic (dis) engagement with hybrid reality television, and their impact on consumption. *Research in Consumer Behavior*, 3, 233-247.
43. Nguyen, T. H., & Gizaw, A. (2014). *Factors that influence consumer purchasing decision of private label food product: A case study of ICA Basic*. School of Business.
44. Nyarko, I. K., Asiamah, V., Agbemava, F., & Tsetse, E. K. (2015). The influence of cerebrity endorcement on consumer buying behavior among the Ghanaian consumers and youths: A study of fan milk Ghana advertising. *The International Journal of Business Management and Review*, 3(11), 1-15.
45. Owusu, A. (2013). Influences of price and quality on consumer purchase of mobile phone in the

“Factors Affecting Consumer Buying Behavior towards Local Brands in Zambia: A Consideration of the Product Preference”

- Kumasi Metropolis in Ghana: A comparative study. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 5(1), 179-186.
46. PwC Africa. (2016). *Prospects in the retail and consumer goods sector in ten sub-Saharan countries*. Pretoria: PwC.
47. Qazzafi, S. (2020). Factor affecting consumer buying behavior: A conceptual study. *International Journal for Scientific Research & Development*, 8(2), 1205-1208.
48. Rani, P. (2014). Factors influencing consumer behaviour. *International Journal of Current Resource Academy Review*, 2(9), 52-61.
49. Richard, A., & Masud, I. (2016). Factors influencing consumer choice in Hotel selection in Ghana. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, 4(11).
50. Rose, F., Zariyawati, M. A., Norazlina, K., Annuar, M. N., & Manisah, O. (2016). Consumers' purchasing decision towards food products of Small and Medium Enterprises. *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 6(4), 836-842.
51. Sarker, M., & Rahman, M. (2017). Consumers' purchasing decision toward Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCGs): An empirical study. *The Comilla University Journal of Business Studies*, 12-38.
52. Saunders, M., Lewis, P., & Thornhill, A. (2012). *Research Methods for Business students* (6 ed.). Pearson Education Limited.
53. Sethna, Z., & Blythe, J. (2016). *Consumer Behavior* (3 ed.). London: SAGE Publications Ltd.
54. Sheith, J. (2011). The impact of emerging markets on marketing: Rethinking existing perspectives and practices. *Journal of Marketing*, 12(2), 75.
55. Shinde, S., & Markle, A. (2012). A study of numerous factors that influences consumers buying behavior towards toothbrush brands at pcmc area Pune. *Golden Research Thoughts*, 6(2), 1-10.
56. Shma. (2012, April Tuesday). *Management Education*. Retrieved from <https://managementation.com/5-stages-of-consumer-buying-decision-process/>
57. Sumarwan, U., & Palupi, E. (2017). understanding consumer motivations in innovative retail formats. *British Food Journal*, 886-899.
58. Sumawidari, I., Darmawan, D. P., & Astiti, N. W. (2013). Factors affecting the purchase of local products and hotel services. *Journal of Agriculture Management*, 1(1).
59. Sarker, M., & Rahman, M. (2017). Consumers' purchasing decision toward Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCGs): An empirical study. *The Comilla University Journal of Business Studies*, 12-38.
60. Tanksale, D., Neellam, N., & Ventatachalam, R. (2014). Consumer decision making styles of young adult consumer when purchasing products in India. *Science Direct*, 211-218.
61. Wirawan, I. G., Julyasih, K. S., Adiartayasa, W., Wijaya, I. M., & Anom, I. P. (2014). Increasing local fruits competitiveness in entering the tourism market in Bali. *International Journal of Biosciences and Biotechnology*, 2(1), 20-25.
62. Wu, S. I., & Jang, J. Y. (2013). The impact of ISO certification on consumers' purchase intention. *Total Quality Management and Business Excellence*, 152-160.
63. Van den Berg, A. (2017). *Factors influencing the purchasing intention of the black middle class in emerging markets for the global brands*. University of Witwatersrand.
64. Vijayalakshmi, R., Gurumoorthy, T. R., Lingavel, G., Arulmozhi, S. J., & kannan, R. M. (2020). Factors influencing consumer buying behaviour towards snacks food products. *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research*, 9(3), 6993-6996.
65. Vindigni, G., Janssen, M. A., & Jager, W. (2002). Organic food consumption: A multi-theoretical framework of consumer decision making. *British Food Journal*, 104(8), 624-642.
66. Wang, C., & Chen, Z. X. (2004). The Consumer Ethnocentrism and Willingness to Buy Local Products in The Domestic Country Setting: The Testing of Moderate Effects of Globalization. *The Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 21(6), 391-400.
67. Yoon, C., & Carpenter, S. M. (2013). Aging and consumer decision making. *Ann N Y & Academy Science*, 235(1), 12.